

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 645704

FREEZE-THAW RESISTANCE OF NORMAL AND HIGH STRENGTH RECYCLED AGGREGATE CONCRETE

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Abstract:

The reuse of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) employed as aggregates for new concrete production, leading to the so-called Recycled Aggregate Concrete (RAC), is an excellent solution from the environmental point of view. In fact, the influence on the use of Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCA) on the resulting RAC's properties has been widely investigated in the recent years, but evaluation of concrete's performance should not be limited only to its behavior under "ordinary" conditions and the characterization of RAC in terms of durability become of extreme importance for structural application. For instance, in cold regions, the concrete's performance over time is closely related to its reaction to freeze-thaw cycles. As a matter of fact, when concrete is exposed to this type of attack, the porous structure tends to absorb water and, then, this water may turn into ice due to temperature variations. This process causes changes in the internal pore structure, reduction in mechanical properties and appearance of cracks. In this context, this study investigates the mechanical and physical performance of different RAC mixtures after the exposure to fast freeze-thaw cycles. Specifically, normal and high strength mixtures (i.e., 35 and 60 MPa) with 100% RCAs were subjected to 150 cycles in which temperature variation from 4°C to -18°C was applied. The experimental results showed that degradation induced by freeze-thaw cycles was more pronounced in the normal strength concrete samples.

Keywords: Recycled Concrete Aggregate, Recycled Aggregate Concrete, Freeze-thaw cycles, Durability, Compressive strength.

1. Introduction

The huge demand of natural resources and the increasing amount of Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) are becoming serious environmental problems due to the rapid development of the construction sector, especially in emerging countries (Loungani *et al.*, 2017). In fact, annually, 871 million tons of CDW are produced in Europe (Eurostat, 2017), while 534 million tons are generated in the United States (EPA, 2014) and the annual CDW production in China exceeds 1.5 billion tons (Huang *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, the re-use of concrete waste, leading to the so-called Recycled Concrete Aggregate (RCAs), for new concrete production is a very promising technical solution for reducing environmental impacts of the construction industry. Generally, RCAs present lower density and higher water absorption in comparison with the aggregates derived from natural sources due to the presence of the Attached Mortar (AM). Another concern is the possible presence of several contaminants (e.g., pieces of bricks, plaster, soil, wood, gypsum, asphalt or plastics) that can be found in RCAs. Some countries limit the percentages

allowed by volume of the use of RCAs in concrete because these contaminants can severely impair the performance of the resulting Recycled Aggregate Concretes (RACs). For example, in Portugal, it is only allowed to use 25% of recycled aggregates in structural concrete (*LNEC E471, 2006*) and in England, only 20% of RCAs in concrete up to 40 MPa of resistance is allowed (*BS 8500-2, 2006*). However, Brazil allows the use of 100% of recycled aggregates in non-structural concretes (*NBR 15116, 2004*), while Italy allows the use of only 15% of recycled aggregates in high strength concretes (55 MPa) (*NTC, 2008*).

The intermittent action of negative and positive temperatures in cold climate regions is one of the main concerns when it comes to the durability of concrete structures, since the freezing of water in the concrete pores can lead to its deterioration, as a consequence of the increase in volume of frozen water. The freezing phenomenon begins in the larger pores and gradually extends to the smaller ones and it is mainly influenced by the pore size, the concentration of dissolved alkalis in the pore gel and the effect of surface tension (*Rojas et al., 2011*). The freeze-thaw resistance of Recycled Aggregate Concrete (RAC) is still not clear because of the wide diversity in the quality and composition of RCAs (*Haitao & Shizhu, 2015; Huda & Shahria Alam, 2015; Liu et al., 2016; Šeps et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2017*).

In this context, the objective of this study is to investigate the influence of freeze-thaw cycles (performed based on *ASTM C666 (2008)* standard) on the resulting physical and mechanical performance of normal (35 MPa) and high strength (60 MPa) concrete including coarse RCAs.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The natural aggregates used in this study were:

- a quartz sand, as fine fraction, with nominal diameter smaller than 4.75 mm;
- a coarse aggregate, as fraction 0 (named “Nat-C0”), composed of granite rocks, with nominal diameter between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm;
- and a coarse aggregate, as fraction 1 (named “Nat-C1”), also composed of granite rocks, with nominal diameter between 9.5 mm and 19 mm.

The concrete waste used herein were derived from a demolition waste recycling plant. The waste was composed of a mixture of different demolition concrete residues, therefore the properties are unknown and the age is indeterminate. Four processing steps produced the Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCAs): crushing, drying, sieving and homogenization. In the first step, a jaw crusher was used to reduce particle size by crushing. Then, the material was air-dried and separated by the use of an industrial mechanical sieve:

- the RCA of nominal diameter between 4.75 mm and 9.5 mm was classified as coarse aggregate fraction 0 (named “RCA-C0”);
- and the RCA of nominal diameter between 9.5 mm and 19 mm was classified as coarse aggregate fraction 1 (named “RCA-C1”).

Finally, the homogenization of the RCAs was performed through the well-known longitudinal blending bed technique (*Pepe et al. (2014)*). Figure 1 shows the coarse aggregates used in this study.

Fig. 1 Coarse aggregates: (a) Nat-C0; (b) Nat-C1; (c) RCA-C0; (d) RCA-C1

The characterization of the aggregates was carried out as follows: coarse aggregates - specific gravity and water absorption tests according to *NBR NM 53 (2009)*; fine aggregate - specific gravity test according to *NBR NM 52 (2009)* and water absorption test according to *NBR NM 30 (2001)*. Table 1 reports the results for the mentioned properties. As expected, the recycled aggregates have lower specific gravity values than the respective natural aggregates and, in addition, the RCAs show high water absorption. The results corroborate the existing relationship between these two properties: the lower the specific gravity of the aggregates, the higher is their absorption. Moreover, the fraction 0 (RCA-C0) present a higher absorption and a smaller specific gravity than fraction 1 (RCA-C1).

Table 1. Properties of the aggregates used in this study.

Properties	Natural aggregates			Recycled aggregates	
	Sand	Nat-C0	Nat-C1	RCA-C0	RCA-C1
Maximum grain diameter (mm)	4.75	9.5	19	9.5	19
Specific gravity (kg/m^3)	2447	2662	2636	2168	2255
Water absorption (%)	0.5	1.5	1.3	7.6	6.1

A high initial strength Portland cement, labeled CPV-ARI according to *NBR 5733 (1991)*, was employed for the concrete mixture production. It is characterized by a compressive strength of 40 MPa at 28 days and a specific gravity of 3181 kg/m^3 .

Finally, a superplasticizer (MC Powerflow 1180), with a solids content of 35% and a specific gravity of 1070 kg/m^3 , was used to control the workability.

2.2 Concrete mixtures composition

The scientific mix-design of the concrete mixtures was carried out according to the Compressive Packing Model (CPM), proposed by *de Larrard (1999)*. The BetonLab Pro 3 software was used to simulate different mix-design of the materials. The method is based on the properties of the constituent materials to calculate the desired concrete properties, assuming that the overall compactness achieved by the dry granular skeleton determines the resulting concrete performance. The behavior of two compressive strength classes was evaluated: a normal strength concrete of 35 MPa and a high strength concrete of 60 MPa. Thus, individual compositions were defined for each mixture, that is, the direct replacement of natural aggregate by RCAs was not performed. For each class, three mixtures were designed: a reference concrete with only natural aggregates (0% RCA), a recycled concrete with 100% RCA in coarse aggregate fraction 0 and a recycled concrete with 100% RCA in the coarse aggregate fraction 1.

The recycled materials were added in dry conditions to the mixture and the absorption was considered in the designed composition: the value used was 50% of total water absorption (obtained experimentally). This value of 50% is based on the studies developed by *Pepe et al. (2016)* and *Amario et al. (2017)*, in

which the authors verified that during the concrete mixing process the RCAs absorb about 50% of their total water absorption capacity, for both coarse aggregate fraction 0 and 1.

Table 2 shows the compositions of the six concrete mixtures. The two concrete mixtures with 100% natural aggregates were named “CX-Nat”, where “X” indicates the resistance class (i.e., 35 MPa and 60 MPa). The four RAC mixtures were named “CX-RCA-Y”, where “X” indicates the resistance class (35 or 60) and “Y” indicates the fraction of RCA that was used (C₀ for fraction 0 and C₁ for fraction 1). The superplasticizer content was 0.2% and 1.5% solids in ratio to cement consumption for the mixtures of 35 MPa and 60 MPa, respectively.

Table 2. Concrete mixtures compositions.

Materials (kg/m ³)	35 MPa			60 MPa		
	C35-Nat	C35-RCA-C0	C35-RCA-C1	C60-Nat	C60-RCA-C0	C60-RCA-C1
RCA-C0 ratio (%)	0	100	0	0	100	0
RCA-C1 ratio (%)	0	0	100	0	0	100
Nat-C1	452	451	0	448	448	0
RCA-C1	0	0	384	0	0	382
Nat-C0	457	0	453	452	0	451
RCA-C0	0	371	0	0	369	0
Sand	868	866	862	860	860	857
Cement	325	345	341	448	464	463
Water	212	214	216	150	145	147

2.3 Mixing procedure and samples preparation

A specific methodology for the mixing process was adopted because of the high water absorption of the RCAs: the total water was divided into two equal parts and the addition of the parts was carried out at different times. The mixing procedure was carried out in the following order: a) mixing for 1 minute all the aggregates; b) addition of half of total water and mixing for 1 minute; c) addition of the cement and mixing for 1 minute; d) addition of the remainder water and the superplasticizer, and mixing all the materials for 8 minutes.

Cylindrical samples of 75 mm diameter and 150 mm height were cast from all concrete mixtures. The fresh concrete was compacted by the use of a vibrating table in two layers for 30 seconds each. Samples were demoulded after 24 hours and maintained at 21°C temperature and 100% humidity until the age of testing.

2.4 Experimental program and testing procedures

Durability tests on concrete subjected to freeze-thaw cycles were executed according to *ASTM C666 (2008)* and started at the age of 28 days. Initially, the specimens were kept immersed in water at 21°C for 48 hours, and then the cycles were started. One cycle consisted in varying the temperature of the specimens from 4°C to -18°C and then reheating to 4°C again. The total time of one cycle was 5 hours and the total number of cycles was 150. The weights of the cylindrical specimens were verified in dry condition, before and at the end of the degradation procedure, allowing the mass variation to be monitored. For a better understanding of the impact of the degradation process, non-degraded specimens were used as reference for comparison. Thus, for all mixtures, non-degraded concrete samples were kept under constant conditions of 21°C temperature and 100% humidity, tested as reference at the same age as the degraded samples.

The slump tests were performed for all mixtures in accordance with *NBR NM 67 (1998)*. The compressive strength tests were performed on cylindrical samples according to *NBR 5739 (2007)*, at a

rate of axial displacement of 0.1 mm/min in Shimadzu 1000 kN mechanical press. Compressive strength tests were performed for all mixtures for 28 days and were also performed for reference samples (without degradation) and 150 freeze-thaw cycles samples. Tensile splitting tests were performed according to *NBR 7222 (2011)* on all mixtures at 28 days.

3. Results and analysis

3.1 Workability and compressive behavior of RAC

Table 3 presents the mean values (and coefficient of variations) of: slump, 28-day compressive strength ($f_{c,28}$), strain at maximum stress ($\epsilon_{c,28}$), Elastic modulus ($E_{c,28}$) and 28-day splitting tensile strength ($f_{t,28}$)

Table 3. Rheological and mechanical properties of concrete mixtures.

Mixture	Slump (mm)	$f_{c,28}$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{c,28}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	$E_{c,28}$ (GPa)	$f_{t,28}$ (MPa)
C35-Nat	175	34.2 (\pm 2.4%)	2898 (\pm 3.2%)	21.3 (\pm 2.1%)	2.7 (\pm 1.7%)
C35-RCA-C0	165	34.4 (\pm 2.2%)	2879 (\pm 5.1%)	21.7 (\pm 0.4%)	2.9 (\pm 4.5%)
C35-RCA-C1	195	33.5 (\pm 2.3%)	2941 (\pm 2.7%)	20.9 (\pm 2.7%)	2.6 (\pm 2.2%)
C60-Nat	165	60.1 (\pm 1.5%)	2665 (\pm 1.7%)	29.1 (\pm 3.2%)	3.9 (\pm 3.2%)
C60-RCA-C0	165	62.6 (\pm 1.0%)	2620 (\pm 3.2%)	31.0 (\pm 3.5%)	4.4 (\pm 2.5%)
C60-RCA-C1	160	59.7 (\pm 0.5%)	2691 (\pm 2.1%)	29.5 (\pm 1.9%)	4.1 (\pm 3.0%)

The slump test results indicate excellent workability for all the produced mixtures with values ranging from 160 mm to 195 mm. In addition, it is notable that RCAs do not influence this property in a negative way, and, all four recycled concrete mixtures presented a rheological behavior that allows adequate moldability. The values obtained for compressive strength were very similar for natural and recycled concretes, within each class. The mix-design method used was able to produce concrete mixtures that reached the desired resistances, and the maximum difference between the desired value and the experimental value was only 4%. This evidence confirms the capacity of the CMP to predict the resistance in cases of RACs. It should be noted that the coefficients of variations obtained for compressive strength are small (below 2.5%), indicating that the RCAs in this study behave homogeneously, a behavior that reinforces the importance of the homogenization stage of the RCAs processing procedure. Figure 2 illustrates the typical stress-strain curves of the compressive strength tests at 28 days and allows confirmation of the similarity between the behaviour of the concrete with 100% natural aggregates and the RACs.

Regarding the strain at maximum stress, the highest values were obtained for the normal class and there were no large variations of results within each class. Also, the Elastic modulus values showed no impact of the use of RCAs, since the mixtures present values of approximately 21 GPa and 30 GPa for the normal strength class and the high strength class, respectively. The results of splitting tensile strength show that the mixture with slightly higher results was that with RCA-C0 for both classes. In general, all the above considerations point out that there were no significant differences in the mechanical behavior between natural concrete and recycled concrete: this is a consequence of the mix-design methodology adopted, which explicitly considered the specific characteristics of the RCAs and their different properties.

Fig. 2 Typical stress-strain curves of 28-day compressive strength tests

3.2 Freeze-thaw resistance of RAC

Table 4 shows the mean values (and coefficient of variations) for reference concrete samples (without degradation, with the same age of the degradation samples) and for concrete samples subjected to 150 freeze-thaw cycles: compressive strength (f_c), strain at maximum stress (ϵ_c), Elastic modulus (E_c) and mass loss (Δ_{ml}) after degradation.

Table 4. Mechanical properties of concrete mixtures after freeze-thaw cycles.

Mixture	No degradation: reference			Degradation: 150 freeze-thaw cycles			
	$f_{c,ref}$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{c,ref}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	$E_{c,ref}$ (GPa)	$f_{c,FT150}$ (MPa)	$\epsilon_{c,FT150}$ ($\mu\epsilon$)	$E_{c,FT150}$ (GPa)	Δ_{ml} (%)
C35-Nat	39.1 ($\pm 3.6\%$)	2837 ($\pm 4.2\%$)	23.5 ($\pm 1.3\%$)	35.8 ($\pm 0.9\%$)	2920 ($\pm 5.1\%$)	22.2 ($\pm 0.4\%$)	1.8
C35-RCA-C0	41.1 ($\pm 4.3\%$)	2792 ($\pm 5.5\%$)	24.4 ($\pm 3.8\%$)	38.0 ($\pm 4.1\%$)	2936 ($\pm 1.8\%$)	22.8 ($\pm 2.9\%$)	1.8
C35-RCA-C1	39.6 ($\pm 2.2\%$)	2850 ($\pm 3.5\%$)	23.6 ($\pm 2.4\%$)	36.8 ($\pm 1.4\%$)	3033 ($\pm 3.2\%$)	21.9 ($\pm 4.1\%$)	1.9
C60-Nat	65.0 ($\pm 1.4\%$)	2549 ($\pm 4.4\%$)	32.3 ($\pm 2.8\%$)	61.2 ($\pm 3.9\%$)	2580 ($\pm 0.8\%$)	30.6 ($\pm 3.6\%$)	1.2
C60-RCA-C0	65.6 ($\pm 4.8\%$)	2498 ($\pm 4.8\%$)	32.9 ($\pm 1.9\%$)	61.9 ($\pm 4.2\%$)	2528 ($\pm 4.8\%$)	31.1 ($\pm 2.5\%$)	1.6
C60-RCA-C1	63.9 ($\pm 2.8\%$)	2522 ($\pm 3.6\%$)	32.5 ($\pm 4.1\%$)	61.1 ($\pm 1.5\%$)	2549 ($\pm 5.1\%$)	31.3 ($\pm 3.0\%$)	1.7

The compressive strength results of the non-degraded reference samples (Table 4), compared to the 28 day values (Table 3), indicate an increase in strength with time, which was expected. This fact is related to hydration processes over time. Following the same logic, there was an increase in the modulus of elasticity (higher stiffness) and a decrease in strain at maximum stress with time, which was also expected. It is worth highlighting that it is not possible to identify any influence of the aggregates on the evolution of resistance with age, since all concrete mixtures had similar behaviors.

The compressive strength results of the degraded samples (Table 4) showed a decrease of the values (when compared with the reference samples) for all the evaluated mixtures. Therefore, the freeze-thaw cycles actually have a negative impact on all concrete mixtures (both in case of NACs and RACs). Figure 3 shows the percentage of this drop in resistance, which ranged from 7.1% to 8.4% for the normal strength class and ranged from 4.4% to 5.8% for the high strength class. That is, the class that suffered the higher impact due to degradation processes was the C35 class, which can be explained by the greater porosity of this class. In general, freezing and thawing damage occurs on the concrete because of its porosity, as it absorbs water and then this water turns to ice at negative temperatures. This phenomenon causes reduction in the resistance, alteration in the internal structure of pores and appearance of cracks in the concrete.

Fig. 3 Percentage of decrease in compressive strength due to freeze-thaw cycles degradation process

However, in spite of their higher capacity of absorption, the recycled concretes presented smaller drop in resistance than the natural concretes, for the two classes. In addition, the mixtures that suffered the least impact caused by the cycles were the concretes produced with the RCA-C1 aggregate. This shows that the particle size of RCA influences in the degradation processes, even though the RCAs have come from the same residue and have been produced with the same equipment and the same processing steps. Thus, the RCA with the best performance in the concrete was the one with the largest nominal diameter (19 mm) independent of the concrete resistance. That is, the RCA with largest nominal diameter allows a greater temperature variation (associated with a change in the volume of water when it turns into ice), causing less negative impacts on the properties of the corresponding concrete. These results are very optimistic: the expected result would be a worse behavior of the RACs compared to the natural concretes due to the greater absorption capacity of the RCAs, and this did not occur in the mixtures evaluated in this study.

On the strain at maximum stress, the cycles caused an increase in these values, which is associated with the resistance values. The modulus of elasticity was also reduced with the fast freeze-thaw cycles for all mixtures in both classes, probably due to changes in the internal pore structure caused by repeated temperature variations. This indicates that the degradation caused a reduction in the stiffness of the concrete, but no relation was identified between the type of aggregate and this behavior. Finally, the values of mass loss show that the class that suffered the higher reductions was the normal strength class, which is consistent with the other results commented above. The difference between the values obtained for mass loss among concretes of the same class was low, but it is worth mentioning that the concretes

that presented the greatest mass loss were the ones that presented the smallest drop in the resistance. Therefore, the authors understand that there is a relationship between these two properties. Thus, these results show that the RCA diameter significantly influences the mechanical, physical and durability properties of the RAC.

The typical stress-strain curves of the degraded samples are shown in Figure 4. It is notable that the behaviors are similar between the mixtures, and the freeze-thaw cycles did not impact on the overall shape of the curves for both the C35 class and the class C60. The normal strength class exhibits higher deformation capacity and the rupture of the specimens occurs through diagonal cracks, while the high strength class exhibits less deformation capacity and the rupture of the specimens is explosive.

Fig. 4 Typical stress-strain curves of compressive strength tests after degradation process (150 freeze-thaw cycles)

4. Conclusions

This study reported the results of experimental tests performed on natural and recycled concrete from different compressive strength classes. The following comments can be highlighted:

- It is possible to produce mixtures of normal and high strength concrete replacing 100% of natural aggregate by RCAs in the fractions investigated in this study without loss in resistance, provided that an appropriate methodology for the mix-design step is adopted, taking into account the specific characteristics of the RCAs;
- The well-known Compressible Packing Model (CPM), originally developed for conventional structural concrete, confirms its accuracy and reliability in predicting properties of the RAC mixtures considered in this study;
- No significant quantitative differences were observed for the RCAs and the corresponding natural concretes, neither in terms of workability in the fresh state, nor in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity in the hardened state at 28 days;
- A drop in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity was identified in all mixtures after the fast freeze-thaw cycles, and all mixtures suffered mass loss at the end of cycles;

- The class that suffered the higher impact due to degradation processes was the normal strength class, which can be explained by the higher porosity of this class;
- These results are very optimistic: in spite of their higher capacity of absorption, the recycled concretes presented smaller drop in resistance than the natural concretes, for the two classes in this study;
- The mixtures that suffered the least impact caused by the cycles were the concretes produced with the RCA-C1 aggregate. This shows that the particle size of RCA influences in the degradation processes, even though the RCAs have come from the same residue and have been produced with the same equipment and the same processing steps;
- Coincidentally, the concrete mixtures that suffered the higher mass loss were those containing RCA-C1, and this fact can be related to the higher durability capacity of these concretes;

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the encouraging conclusions described above are consequences of the appropriate mix-design methodology adopted for RACs and further experimental studies are required, exploring other RCAs variables to confirm the preliminary results obtained in this study

Acknowledgement

The study is part of SUPERCONCRETE Project (H2020-MSCA-RISE-2014, n. 645704): the Authors wish to acknowledge the financial contribution of the EU-funded Horizon 2020 Programme. More specifically, it was partly developed during the mobilities of both Prof. Romildo D. Toledo Filho at the University of Salerno (Italy), and Dr. Marco Pepe at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (Brazil).

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